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Ikechukwu Stephen Okolie

Xenophobic Attacks: Their Effects on the Economic and Diplomatic Affairs of Nigeria and South Africa.

Ikechukwu Stephen Okolie

Department of Political Science, University of Maiduguri, Borno State Nigeria

ikechukwu.okolie@unimaid.edu.ng

+2347032112492

Abstract

The push factors of xenophobic attacks against migrants in South Africa are enormous. This paper looks at the aftermath of xenophobic attacks on the South Africa-Nigeria economic and diplomatic affairs. It seeks to examine the causes, the implications of xenophobic attacks on Nigeria-South Africa diplomatic and economic affairs, and the effects of xenophobia and xenophobic attacks against Nigerian residents in South Africa. Lack of access to economic opportunities, poverty, and lack of jobs and means of livelihood were some of the triggers of xenophobic attacks in South Africa. The paper used secondary sources such as articles, unpublished dissertations and tabloids for presentation. The study showed that the xenophobic attack on migrants in South Africa has claimed the lives of over 117 Nigerians; and that it will take political will from Pretoria to tackle the menace of xenophobia in South Africa. The paper recommended, among others, that Nigerian government should employ carrot and stick diplomacy when dealing with South Africa on issues affecting the interest of Nigeria and Nigerians.

Keywords: Xenophobic, xenophobia, Nigeria, South Africa, Apartheid, Migrants

Introduction

Globally, xenophobia is a phenomenon that cuts across societies and cultures, with an antecedent of hostility and discrimination against migrants. The issue of xenophobia can be traced back to the history of mankind, where non-nationals who migrated to Greek city states were seen as sub-humans by the Greeks. Across the continent of Africa, from North to South, there is an increase in the rate of xenophobia and discrimination against fellow African migrants based on colour, religion, and race, which is a daily occurrence (Ibrahim, Dele, and Ukeaja, 2019).

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The issue of xenophobia is anchored on political beliefs of segregation, marginalisation, and discrimination, with the mentality that migrants are not the same as citizens and must not be welcomed or accorded the rights and privileges enjoyed by the nationals. It is also a belief that migrants should be accorded lesser significance by nationals and the government. Xenophobia has caused so many problems that it has led to the disintegration of some countries and the flushing out of tribal minorities (Fetzer, 2000).

According to Fetzer (2000), the people of the Northern Hemisphere always observe migrants with mistrust, apprehension, and detestation, not minding that the cheaper labour of these migrants is needed by the nationals. Due to the illegal status of the majority of the migrants, it is always difficult for them to look for justice in the court of law, even when it comes to employment and rights infringement. Oftentimes, these illegal migrants are rounded up, maltreated, humiliated, and sent back to their country of origin. Studies have shown that non-nationals are more vulnerable to attacks by nationals because of their alien status.

According to a report by some international organisations and human rights observers, bodily attacks against migrants by Americans were on the rise three decades ago, and similarly, reports of migrants being killed became rampant 16 years ago (Fetzer, 2000).

Xenophobic violence has also been recorded elsewhere outside the shores of the United States. A political party in Switzerland (SPP) was alleged to have indulged in prejudice and intolerant sentiment by distributing derogatory flyers for campaigns. The campaign flyers pictured a pale traditionalist pushing the dark animal off the Swiss national ensign. The SPP has a party mandate to change the punitive law to empower magistrates with absolute power to repatriate migrants found guilty of committing criminal acts after the completion of their prison term. The harshest aspect of the proposed law was that even if the criminal offender was a juvenile, the entire family of the criminal was deported when judgement was delivered (Crush, 2000).

Furthermore, Crush (2008) noted that marginalisation, discrimination, and segregation based on the assumption of being a migrant have been going on in the continent of Africa prior to conquest by the Europeans but became institutionalised in the era of colonial rule. Enclosed backgrounds and feelings of nationalism have also been going on in the continent of Africa for centuries. The modern-day xenophobic attacks against migrants are results of the current behaviour of this attribute.

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Violent attacks against migrants and African migrants are becoming a daily occurrence and increasingly rampant, stimulated by aggression, detestation, and mistrust due to division in localities (SAMP, 2004). After the independence of South Africa and the defeat of the apartheid regime, there is still misgiving about trust, marginalisation, racial discrimination, economic discrimination, and inequality, as well as oppression in the new nation (Gqola, 2001, cited in Hendricks, 2005, and Trimikliniotis, Gordon, and Zondo, 2008). There is no general agreement about the current situation of things in the modern-day Republic of South Africa after decades of governance by the African National Congress (ANC), which came into power after independence and defeated the apartheid regime. There has been a constant discussion as to pace, future, and direction in the post-apartheid regime in South Africa (Trimikliniotis et al., 2008).

Lester, Nel, and Binns (2000) noted that the democratic governance in South Africa, the rainbow nation, has shown that the masses have the same electoral power as the elite, but there is a wide inequality gap in their society and country. The inequality gap that was in existence during the apartheid regime in South Africa is still visible after years of majority leadership. This has shown that the apartheid structure is yet to be dismantled in the present-day Republic of South Africa after years of political independence. The minority in South Africa is still in control of the economy and means of production, which has widened the inequality gap.

Statement of Problem

The current xenophobic attacks directed at Nigerian migrants' resident in the rainbow state of South Africa have shown a high rate of discrimination and segregation, as well as hatred towards aliens, in the post-apartheid Republic of South Africa, which is one of the biggest and most developed economies on the African continent. The current xenophobic attack against migrant Nigerians resident in the Republic of South Africa led to the murder of over sixty people and the displacement of many, prompting the Federal Government of Nigeria to act swiftly by taking diplomatic actions against the government of South Africa. The properties and business premises, as well as other means of livelihood of many Nigerians living in South Africa, were set ablaze and looted by the local mobs (Alli, 2008).

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The Republic of South Africa is extremely well known in Africa for its increasingly xenophobic and violent attacks on migrants living in the rainbow nation. Violent xenophobic riots and attacks against migrants in the Republic of South Africa are seen to have drastically been on the increase following the entrenchment of a democratic system of government and post-apartheid (Okolie, 2021). On February 11, 2022, three Nigerians were killed by a South African angry mob who alleged they were drug dealers. The violent xenophobic attacks against Nigerians in the Republic of South Africa have continued unabated. Recently, many Nigerians were killed in Vereeniging, near Johannesburg, by members of the community at a taxi rank. The Republic of South Africa has continued to be a graveyard for the teeming young Nigerians over the years. According to recent reports, more than 128 migrant Nigerians have been murdered in the Republic of South Africa since the year 2019.

One can trace relations between Nigeria and the Republic of South Africa back to the histories of both states. When the British Union Jack was lowered and replaced with the national flag of Nigeria, which is green and white, on October 1, 1960, it ushered in an independent country called Nigeria. After independence, Nigeria, as a big brother on the continent, began to support the liberation and decolonization struggles of other African states still under the control of colonial governments. The Republic of South Africa became the centre of attention for the Nigerian government due to the oppressive rule and subjugation going on in the country under the apartheid regime. In a move to free the Republic of South Africa from the grip of the apartheid regime, the Nigerian government began to fund and support liberation groups and movements in South Africa. Nigeria also offered asylum to South African political activists who were hunted by the apartheid regime in their country. Africans, likewise Nigerians, began to migrate to South Africa after the defeat of the apartheid regime and the establishment of a democratic system of government. The new rainbow nation witnessed an influx of migrants with a sense of Africanism and brotherhood (Ogunnubi and Amusan, 2018). The massive influx of registered and unregistered migrants in the Republic of South Africa has become irritating, which has led to continued aggression, violent attacks, discrimination, and hatred (Isike and Isike, 2012).

On September 3, 2019, properties of Nigerian nationals in Johannesburg, South Africa, were destroyed by angry local mobs engineered by leaders of their communities. The attack led to the murder of five migrants in Johannesburg and the roundup of 80

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people by the security agencies. The local mobs, made up of unemployed South African youths, destroyed shops and business outlets, as well as other properties owned by migrants, especially Nigerians (Onke, 2019). The most affected people in the recent xenophobic attack were citizens of Nigeria who reside in the Republic of South Africa. Angry mobs destroyed investments with migrant ownership and killed and burned unarmed Nigerians who were victims. To register their displeasure over the maltreatment of Nigerians in South Africa by the locals, Nigerians requested that business enterprises owned by South Africa operating in Nigeria, such as PEP, GAME, Shoprite, MTN, Protea Hotel, and Multichoice, among others, be sanctioned (Okolie, 2021).

Nigerians were angry at the number of their nationals who were murdered in the violent xenophobic attacks in South Africa, knowing well that the government in Pretoria could do better by protecting migrants in South Africa. The outcry by Nigerians prompted the Nigerian government to evoke her ambassador to Pretoria and boycott the World Economic Summit (Ameh, 2019). Over three hundred Nigerians were airlifted from the Republic of South Africa by Air Peace, an indigenous Nigerian personal airliner, which offered services free from September 11, 2019 (Okolie, 2021).

It is unfortunate in a time like this that the government and people of South Africa have forgotten the contributions of Nigeria and Nigerians to their freedom and decided to be aggressive and hostile towards Nigerians living in their country. During the liberation movement in South Africa, the Nigerian government ordered a compulsory deduction of a certain percentage from the monthly wages of public servants in Nigeria to support the liberation movement against the oppressive apartheid regime in the country (Okolie, 2021). A report has shown that the Nigerian government committed a whopping sum of \$61 billion between 1960 and 1995 in the fight against apartheid rule in the Republic of South Africa (Babalola, 2017).

In a bid to douse tension, the government of South Africa shut down her diplomatic offices in Abuja and Lagos, Nigeria, and likewise announced the interim closure of other South African investments in Nigeria (Neil, 2019). As a mark of solidarity and displeasure, super stars who were to perform in a concert organised in South Africa cancelled their invitation to the show. The effects of this behavioural act have caused Nigerians to cut down on their visits to South Africa, especially businessmen and tourists (Okolie, 2021). This study therefore, attempts to scrutinise the

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impacts of xenophobic attacks on Nigeria's and South Africa's economic and diplomatic affairs.

Objectives of the Study

- To examine the effects of xenophobia on Nigerian and Republic of South African affairs.
- To scrutinise the causes of violent xenophobic attacks against Nigerians who reside in South Africa.
- Highlight the implications of violent xenophobic attacks against Nigerians in South Africa.

Conceptualization

According to Matunhu (2008), xenophobia is a behavioural inclination of unfriendliness, violence, and discrimination against what is seen as alien to nationals. According to Smelser and Baltes (2001), the term xenophobia comes from two Greek words: "xenos," which means alien, and "phobos," which means apprehension. This behaviour is based on racial, religious, and cultural factors, as well as national intolerance. The fear of the unknown or against migrants has prompted the intolerant and xenophobic traits in humans to protect certain interests against foreign access. These interests that humans intend to protect against aliens can be social, economic, or political.

Furthermore, Mantunhu (2008) defined xenophobia as an intolerant displacement of hate, mistrust, and discrimination against migrants. In the words of Klaude (2001), xenophobia is the behaviour of uncomfotability against foreigners, which most of the time has led to violent attacks around the global against migrants.

Accordingly, Crowther (1995) noted that the concept of xenophobia is an extreme hatred, misconception, and distrust against persons who are migrants from other countries of the world, irrespective of race and colour. In the submission made by Khosa and Malitani (2014), xenophobia has become endemic in all the cities and locations in South Africa where non-nationals are called derogatory names like "*kwerekwere*" which means alien.

Several studies have shown that the menace of xenophobia is inherent in almost all the fabrics of South African society. This goes a long way to buttressing the fact that

post-apartheid South Africa is still battling with the structures left by the oppressive regime (Dodson and Oelofse 2000). Bond, Ngwane, and Amisi (2010) pointed out that xenophobia and attacks against migrants are politically motivated, which is the hallmark of apartheid South Africa and the post-apartheid era engineered by Pretoria against African and non-African migrants. Xenophobia is the hatred of nationals of a state against aliens and non-nationals living in the host country or state.

The Trends of Xenophobic Attacks on Nigerian Residents in South Africa

The continued violent xenophobic attack against migrant's resident in South Africa by angry local mob gangs is not a new thing in the country. These attacks have led to backlash against South Africa in the international community and other African countries. One can trace the violent xenophobic attacks against African migrants in South Africa to when angry local gangs from the Alexandra suburb of Johannesburg destroyed, looted, and set ablaze shops and houses of migrants in 1995. These African migrants were forcefully taken to the security agencies by the local gangs, who demanded their instant eviction from South Africa. In the year 2008, a violent xenophobic riot erupted in South Africa that spread across the countryside and targeted African migrants from Sub-Saharan Africa, which led to the deaths of over 60 migrants and destroyed businesses owned by these migrants worth millions of dollars (Burchard, 2015).

In the fall of 2000, Nigerians in South Africa became victims of targeted violent xenophobic attacks by the local youths and gangs, who accused them of employment and economic deprivation. The violent xenophobic attack led to the deaths of five African migrants and two Nigerians who were murdered in cold blood in their apartment at Cape Flats in Cape Town, South Africa (Bello and Tunde, 2017).

Since 2000, Nigerians in the rainbow nation of South Africa have become targets and victims of continued violent xenophobic attacks against migrants. Between the years 2014 and 2017, about 81 Nigerians were reportedly killed by angry South African mobs. On February 18, 2017, Nigerians in South Africa were attacked, leading to looting and burning of their business premises (Bello and Tunde, 2017). On February 18 and 27, 2017, Nigerians were again attacked by local South African gangs who looted and set ablaze their shops and other means of livelihood. At the end of 2017, it was reported that over 160 Nigerians had lost their lives to xenophobic attacks (Wakili and Salau, 2017).

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Analysis and evaluation after the incident indicated that Nigerians resident in South Africa who were victims of xenophobic attacks lost investments that ran into hundreds and millions of USD, which is the aftermath of the unabated and constant violent attacks and mob action in South Africa (Okolie, 2021).

A country-wide 2004 survey carried out by the University of Witwatersrand on residents of the inner city of Johannesburg revealed that about 65 percent of nationals supported the deportation of migrants from the Rainbow State. A handful of South Africans viewed deporting or evicting the white minority out of South Africa as a top priority (Okolie and Joseph, 2021).

The Effects of Xenophobia on Nigeria-South Africa Relations

The continued and unabated attacks against Nigerian migrants in the rainbow nation of South Africa have led to many diplomatic cold wars and boycotts between the Republic of South Africa and Nigeria. The Nigerian government and her citizens have been on the receiving end of these unprovoked attacks and killings of Nigerians in South Africa. This inhuman act by local mobs against African migrants has led to a diplomatic cold war between South Africa and many other African states, especially Nigeria. Nigerians bore the brunt of most of the violent xenophobic attacks and unlawful killings in the Republic of South Africa (Okolie, 2021).

In a statement issued by the Special Assistant to Mohammadu Buhari, the President, on foreign affairs and diaspora, no fewer than 117 Nigerian citizens were unlawfully murdered in the Republic of South Africa between 2016 and 2018 from violent xenophobic attacks (Vanguard, 2018). This horrendous killing of Nigerian citizens in the rainbow nation of South Africa has affected Nigeria-South Africa affairs in so many ways. The effects of unabated violent xenophobic attacks against Nigerian citizens in South Africa can be viewed through the political/diplomatic, economic, social-cultural, and educational dimensions. These attacks have severe effects on the diplomatic and economic relations of Nigeria and South Africa (Okolie, 2021).

Political and diplomatic effects

Diplomatically, the government of South Africa has been receiving backlash from Nigeria and other African states over the continued violent xenophobic attacks on migrants in the country. Over the years, Nigerians have been the most targeted victims of

xenophobia in South Africa, which has affected diplomatic relations between the two countries. There are severe implications if both countries, especially South Africa, do not do the needful to tackle the menace of xenophobia attacks. The political and diplomatic effects of xenophobia on South Africa-Nigeria relations are:

- i. It might lead to severing of diplomatic ties between the two countries if the unabated attack against Nigerians resident in South Africa is not politically tackled by the government in Pretoria.
- ii. Nigeria is seen as the big brother on the continent of Africa and has shown that capacity over the decades in words and action. Diplomatic altercations between Nigeria and South Africa will affect the spirit of Africanism in the continent because brotherhood is the key factor uniting Africa. The diplomatic altercation might affect the African harmony and one-voice submission in international politics.
- iii. Imposition of a visa ban or stringent visa requirements and policies for intending travellers to both countries as a means of showing the power of diplomatic hegemony. This move will greatly affect the movement of people between the two countries, especially businessmen and tourists.

After the deadly 2008 xenophobic attacks against African migrants and Nigerians resident in the rainbow nation of South Africa, both states have initiated strategies to fashion out a diplomatic solution. This led to the signing of a memorandum of understanding (MoU) in 2013 by Nigeria and South Africa to redefine diplomatic terms and conditions, likewise preventing potential xenophobic attacks (Babalola, 2017). Nevertheless, violent xenophobic attacks against Nigerians in South Africa have continued unabated after the MoU was signed between the two countries. In 2015, the High Commissioner and Consul General of Nigeria to the Republic of South Africa were invited home for deliberation and consultation on the violent xenophobic attacks on Nigeria in the cities of Johannesburg and Durban (Channels Television, 2015).

Economic effects

Economically, there are effects of violent xenophobic attacks on migrants on the economy and economic relations between Nigeria and South Africa. The unwillingness to tackle the high spate of xenophobic attacks against Nigerians led to the boycott of all South African businesses and companies operating in Nigeria. The boycott by Nigerians

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affected the economic and financial fortunes of these South African companies operating in Nigeria, especially MTN, GAME, Shoprite, PEP, and Multichoice, among others. For fear of reprisal attacks by Nigerians, these companies and businesses were shut down in the short term.

The Nigeria-South Africa Chamber of Commerce stated that the effects of violent xenophobic attacks in the rainbow nation and the retaliation from Nigerians are a great threat to the economies of Nigeria, South Africa, and Africa as a whole, considering the fact that both states have the biggest economies on the continent of Africa. According to the chamber,

There is a high volume of trading between the Republic of South Africa and Nigeria which amounted to R174 million in 1999, a volume of about R3 billion in 2008, and R66 billion in 2014. Nigeria is the main exporter of crude oil to South Africa, with an export of R38.5 billion worth of crude oil in 2015 (www.sancc.co.za).

The destruction and shutting down of businesses in Nigeria and South Africa will lead to the loss of jobs and economic activities, thereby increasing the rate of unemployment and crime prevalence in both countries (Eze and Akena, 2017).

There are at least 121 South African multinational corporations (MNCs) and companies operating in different sectors of the Nigerian economy, from telephony to aviation, manufacturing, construction, banking, hospitality, entertainment, and retail shops, which are easy targets for reprisal attacks because of violent xenophobic attacks against Nigerians in South Africa (Mbamalu, 2017; Unah, 2017).

Social and Cultural Effects

Socially and culturally, Africans are attached to each other due to their shared historical background and political experience in the hands of the colonial government during the era of colonialism and the slave trade. Different nations, societies, and communities in Africa are traditionally and culturally linked to each other, which has led to the spirit of African brotherhood and Africanism. After the end of colonial political rule in Africa, which brought about divide and rule, balkanization, and identity race, Africans began to

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reunite in a bid to chart a new course for themselves by upholding their norms, culture, belief system, and tradition. But the current spike of violent xenophobic attacks against African migrants by their South African brothers has led to social and cultural dislocation, which was going on through inter-marriages. According to Eze and Agena (2017), discrimination, humiliation, and xenophobic attacks against African migrants by local gangs in South Africa have led to questioning of African unity and Africanism. The constant unresolved xenophobic attacks on African migrants have severe social and cultural effects, which include uncertainty, suspicion, social and cultural isolation, disunity, and identity problems.

i. Social and cultural isolation: African migrants in South Africa will be forced to isolate themselves socially and culturally from the nationals because of the fear of being attacked. This social and cultural isolation will lead to a reduction in friendships and marriages between African migrants and South African nationals. Most of the male and female Nigerians resident in South Africa are married to South Africans for integration. But the tide and social bond is beginning to disintegrate, thereby creating a social and cultural gap between the two countries. Today, migrants and Nigerians in South Africa no longer socialise because of fear.

ii. Uncertainty: Since African migrants, especially Nigerians, are targets of violent xenophobic attacks by angry South African youths, their lives and safety become uncertain because the government is not providing protection, which has made them vulnerable to unprovoked attacks. In most cases, this has made the victims to form retaliation groups.

iii. Identify problem: Most of the kids born in South Africa through intermarriage are suffering from identity problems due to dislocation caused by constant violent xenophobic attacks on African migrants in South Africa, especially Nigerians. Most of the Nigerians married to South Africans have abandoned their children in South Africa and left for the safety of their lives, thereby leaving these kids to suffer from identity problems. Most of these kids are discriminated against by their South African brothers, who treat them as foreigners.

The unabated menace of violent xenophobic attacks in the post-apartheid Republic of South Africa for decades has infused fright, suspicion, and mistrust in the mentality of

African migrants, especially Nigerian victims (Ogunnoiki and Adeyemi, 2019). Most of the Nigerian victims of violent xenophobic attacks in South Africa are suffering from emotional and psychological problems, especially Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder because of the destruction of their means of livelihood and investment, which led to bankruptcy (Ogunnoiki and Adeyemi, 2019).

Educational and exchange programmes effects

South Africa is a choice destination for the teeming population of Nigerian students who are seeking quality education and eager to obtain international degrees and qualifications. This is because of the quality of university education and the global position of South African higher education institutions. South African universities are well equipped and funded, which makes them competitive with universities in the western world in terms of teaching and research (Okolie, 2021).

With thousands of Nigerians living in South Africa, it has become one of the most popular study destinations for Nigerian students. Nigerian students studying various courses, both undergraduate and postgraduate, in South Africa are found in the top five South African universities (Okolie, 2021). These large numbers of Nigerian students studying in South Africa are sources of foreign cash inflow to the South African economy and universities. Since the rise in violent xenophobic attacks against migrants in South Africa, particularly on Nigerians, this has affected and discouraged prospective Nigerian students intending to study at South African universities (Okolie, 2021). These prospective Nigerian students are now moving towards Turkey and Cyprus to study, which have quality universities. This change in study destination has caused South Africa to lose cash inflow from Nigerian students into her economy and universities (Okolie, 2021).

The Causes of Xenophobic Attacks on Nigerian Residents in South Africa

Several factors that triggered the violent xenophobic attacks on African migrants in South Africa, particularly Nigerians, were developed from the amalgam of literature on xenophobia; the following reasons have been adduced as being the propelling reasons for the said attacks in South Africa in 2008, 2015, and 2019 (Ijisakin and Fakanbi, 2019);

Firstly, the cause of the attack can be looked at from the angle of governmental neglect of the essential necessities of the people (Anyim, Chijioke, and Anyim-Ben,

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2019). It can therefore be said hypothetically that frustration with the government precipitated aggression among the locals against the non-South Africans. Even though some would put this down as a misplaced transfer of aggression, it holds some logic that the people, in their bid to vent their grievance, decided to deal with aliens (Anyim et al., 2019). Morris (2008), cited in Ijisakin and Fakanbi (2019), submitted that the alleged lackadaisical attitude of the South African government and the abandonment of communities by Pretoria triggered the violence.

Similarly, competition over limited resources constituted another logical argument to buttress the constant xenophobic attacks against migrants in South Africa. Dodson, in Ijisakin and Fakanbi (2019), commented that South Africans saw African migrants as threats and competitors over scarce resources and opportunities that they believed were solely meant for them. Sharp (2008) adds that wealthy South Africans abhor the idea of paying taxes to provide essential services for non-South Africans who escaped from their different countries due to bad leadership, political incompetence, and economic mismanagement.

On a lighter note, Dodson and Oelofse (2000) noted that gender and sexuality have a role to play in the attacks because of the competition between male African migrants and their South African counterparts over ladies. It is also noted that male African migrants were inclined to flashing money around, thereby stealing the South African women from local men. In the area of jobs, illegal immigrants to South Africa were ready to take up any job without the corresponding benefits and at any wage rate just to survive.

Poverty and unemployment are other factors that are causing the violent attacks against African migrants in South Africa. One can therefore say tentatively that poverty increases xenophobic attacks against migrants in South Africa. This hostility towards African migrants can be placed at the door of economic deprivation, which is a precursor to poverty. This theory holds that poverty begets frustration and, by extension, aggression (Ijisakin and Fakanbi, 2019).

Another reason for the attacks could be that, most times, African migrants may have a different cultural, traditional, and religious belief system from that of the nationals. Classen in (Ijisakin and Fakanbi, 2019), corroborating this position, observes that the cultural and religious differences of Mozambicans or Zimbabweans (formerly Rhodesia) are not too different from those of the South Africans; that of Nigerians and

Eritrea, for example, were poles apart from the South Africans's cultural and religious beliefs, and this made them feel insecure and threatened. A similar view to this is the theory of relative deprivation. This theory holds that natives naturally deserve better living conditions than immigrants, who do not have a stake in the Commonwealth of South Africa. They contend that, in the event of any eventuality, the immigrants have their various countries to run to, but they have nowhere to go (Ijisakin and Fakanbi, 2019).

The Effects of Xenophobic Attacks on Nigerian Residents in South Africa

The unabated violent xenophobic attacks against Nigerians resident in the Republic of South Africa, the rainbow nation, have some effects. These implications, according to Okolie (2021), can be highlighted as follows:

Closure of businesses

Most of the Nigerian residents in South Africa engage in various types of trading and service provision to the inhabitants of their neighbourhood, and in doing so, they also provide employment opportunities to South Africans. The incessant xenophobic attacks have forced many Nigerian businessmen and entrepreneurs to close down their businesses over fear of destruction and looting. This has also affected labour and income generation by the national, municipal, and provincial governments in South Africa.

Forced relocation to other countries

Nigerian residents in the rainbow nation of South Africa who are in the official and casual sectors providing and rendering different forms of services in South Africa and contributing to the economic development and growth of the country are forced to relocate to other safer countries where their services are needed and their lives are protected.

Threat to life and death

Nigerians no longer socialise with locals due to fear of being attacked or killed by local gangs. Over the years, many Nigerian citizens have been killed in South Africa due to violent xenophobic attacks against migrants. Nigerians have become victims and targets of the xenophobia conspiracy in South Africa. There is a conspiracy between the locals

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and security agencies in South Africa to round up Nigerians and humiliate them. On February 11, 2022, three Nigerians were murdered by a South African mob in Vereeniging, near Johannesburg.

Psychological and emotional trauma

Losing one's investment and means of livelihood can be traumatic to the victims, considering years of hard work, commitment, and sacrifices made. Many Nigerians who were victims of violent xenophobic attacks in South Africa saw their shops looted and properties set ablaze by the mob and are now suffering from psychological trauma and depression.

Conclusion

There are several factors that have led to the prevalence of violent xenophobic attacks against African migrants' residents and businesses in the Republic of South Africa. These attacks have affected the economic and diplomatic relations of South Africa with other African states, especially Nigeria, which South Africa sees as a rival on the continent of Africa. Nigerians protested against the continued killing of their brothers in South Africa by boycotting businesses and companies that are owned by South Africans in Nigeria. Other African countries whose citizens were killed in South Africa and their means of livelihoods destroyed by the local mob also retaliated.

The pursuit of foreign policy and state interests between both countries has caused deep-rooted competition for supremacy, hegemony, and rivalry in Africa. For Nigeria to take her rightful place in Africa and to become the hegemon and power to reckon with, she needs to be more competitive in the world economy in order to command respect from South Africa. Nigeria must develop her industrial sector and base to displace South Africa as the most developed economy on the continent in order to regain and position herself as a dominant power and player.

Strong economic and political cooperation between Nigeria and the Republic of South Africa is key to the development process in Africa. Both countries should not relegate or underrate countries like Egypt, Kenya, Angola, Algeria, and Tunisia when it comes to African discourse.

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Recommendation

However, to tackle and reduce the prevalence of violent xenophobic attacks against African migrants in South Africa, it requires concerted efforts and political will from Pretoria. The government in Pretoria should, as a matter of sincerity, protect and respect the rights and lives of migrants residing in the country. It is important for Pretoria to abide by all laws, treaties, and regulations pertaining to human rights and refrain from encouraging inhuman acts meted out on African migrants, which have angered Africans.

The following recommendations are made:

- i. Nigerian government has to employ carrot and stick diplomacy when dealing with the government in Pretoria on issues affecting Nigerian interests and Nigerians living in South Africa.
- ii. Nigerian government and her political leaders should always compel the South African government to educate and tell her citizens the role and sacrifices Nigerians and the Nigerian government played for their liberation from the apartheid regime.
- iii. Nigerian government should redefine her foreign policy and diplomatic relations with South Africa.
- iv. The South African government in Pretoria should desist from institutional and political collusion in these attacks on African migrants and Nigerians living in the country.
- v. In order to deter xenophobes from carrying out xenophobic attacks as well as the extrajudicial killings of migrants by the police, the South African government should arrest, prosecute, and convict offenders and their collaborators.

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